

RADIOBLOCKS

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List of acronyms

AARTFAAC	Amsterdam-ASTRON Radio Transients Facility And Analysis Center
ADC	Analog to Digital Converter
ALMA	Atacama Large Millimeter/submillimeter Array
API	Application Programming Interface
CPU	Central Processing Unit
DMA	Direct Memory Access
DPDK	Data Plane Development Kit
EMIB	Embedded Multi-Die Interconnect Bridges
FPGA	Field-Programmable Gate Array
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
HBM	High Bandwidth Memory
HPC	High Performance Computing
IP	Internet Protocol
JIVE, JIV-ERIC	Joint Institute for VLBI ERIC
NIC	Network Interface Connectors
PCIe	Peripheral Component Interconnect express
RDMA	Remote Direct Memory Access
RoCEv2	RDMA over Converged Ethernet version 2
RX	Receive
SOC-FPGA	System On Chip FPGA
SOM	System On Module
SPEAD	Streaming Protocol for Exchanging Astronomical Data
TCP	Transmission Control Protocol
UBx	Université de Bordeaux
UDP	User Datagram Protocol
VLBI	Very Long Baseline Interferometry
WIFP	WSU IF Processor
WSU	Wideband Sensitivity Upgrade

Abstract

This document presents the prototype development that aims to investigate the feasibility of high-bandwidth data transport over Ethernet using DPDK and RDMA technologies.

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1 Introduction

The primary goal of this demonstrator is to achieve and potentially exceed 400 GbE data transfer rates for high speed data transport in radio telescope systems. While both DPDK and RDMA technologies promise significant performance gains, they present distinct advantages and challenges. The background and analysis of these high speed data handling techniques has previously been described in RADIOBLOCKS Deliverable 4.2 [1]. DPDK offers a flexible approach, bypassing the operating system kernel for direct hardware access. This allows for easier integration into existing systems and the potential to scale to larger demonstrators. In contrast, RDMA, while potentially offering high performance at a reduced load on the receiver side, requires specialized (FPGA) firmware and is more complex to implement.

By comparing DPDK and RDMA, we aim to identify the most suitable technology for high-bandwidth data transport in our target applications. For the demonstration of high bandwidth data transport in combination with a representative application, we aim for two key proof-of-concept implementations:

1. A multi-front-end to single back-end system to demonstrate high-speed data aggregation and processing.
2. A wideband front-end integrated with a representative back-end application, showcasing the complete signal path from digitization to correlation.

The focus of the prototype of the demonstrator, described in this deliverable, is on a smaller-scale system based on the ALMA WSU development involving two front-ends and a single back-end, each front-end delivering 20 GHz sideband.

In this deliverable we present an RDMA implementation validated in simulation and a DPDK implementation demonstrated up to a bandwidth of 1.2Tb/s. We also present the first version of the high speed data transport prototype, which will evolve in the future to be fully integrated in the ALMA WSU IF Processor validation chain.

The performance evaluation will encompass throughput, CPU load, energy consumption, and implementation complexity for both technologies. The results will be applicable to both distributed radio telescope systems and VLBI correlators.

2 DPDK

2.1 Introduction

In this chapter we describe the design, considerations, implementation and demonstration of the Data Plane Development Kit (DPDK), a software based approach to efficiently receive high-speed data transfers on a host system. The DPDK has been introduced before in [1].

For development and demonstration we use two *Grace Hopper Superchip* [2] systems. These innovative systems do not only contain one of the most powerful GPUs to date, the traditional PCIe link between CPU and GPU is replaced by NVLink, that provides seven times more bandwidth than PCIe gen 5 (see Figure 1). This essentially eliminates the I/O bottleneck of discrete GPUs. The figure also shows four PCIe links (on the left), but in practice, Grace Hopper systems have at most three PCIe slots available for network interfaces (NICs). Each slot can hold one 400 Gb/s Ethernet (GbE) NIC or a dual-port 200 GbE NIC, for a total of 1200 Gb/s of Ethernet connectivity, six times more than a PCIe gen 4 GPU can handle.

Figure 1: Schematics of the Grace Hopper Superchip (source: NVIDIA).

However, faster hardware alone is not enough to achieve 1.2 Tb/s at the application level. Such data rates cannot be handled by the Operating System (OS): the interrupt, context switching, and packet-copying overheads are prohibitive. And as we will show below, even the CPU memory is too slow to act as a packet buffer. We need techniques that bypass the OS, and stream packet data directly from the NICs into GPU memory. Normally, one would use RDMA techniques like GPUdirect [3] for this, but as the data comes from FPGAs, this option is not available. Alternatively the FPGA packet transfer mechanism can be adapted to support RDMA as described in chapter 3. In this work instead, we use the Data Plane Development Kit (DPDK) [4] to receive and handle network packets without OS overhead, and we use a recent DPDK addition, called *GPUdev* [5], that allows Ethernet packets to be processed directly by the GPU. This also proved to be an essential technique to achieve high data rates.

Through a combination of software and hardware innovations, we demonstrate a GPU cor-

relator that receives and processes 1196 Gb/s of Ethernet packets, a 6–20-fold improvement over previous-generation GPU correlators. This result shows that in general I/O is no longer the GPU’s Achilles heel.

We explain the techniques and optimizations that are necessary to achieve this data rate. We analyze the network, CPU, and GPU performance, show how to reduce the energy use, and discuss the strengths and weaknesses of the DPDK approach.

Although this study is driven by the challenges from radio astronomy, the results apply to (GPU) applications from any domain that demands high data rates, especially in situations where the use of RDMA is not possible.

This chapter is structured as follows. In Section 2.2, we provide some background information on radio telescopes, GPU correlators, and DPDK. Section 2.3 describes several DPDK-based implementations of a GPU correlator, for which we analyze the performance and energy efficiency in Section 2.4. Section 2.5 discusses advantages and disadvantages of the DPDK approach, and Section 2.6 concludes.

2.2 Background

Figure 2: Data flow from antennas to GPU correlator systems.

As a quick recap, in this section, we briefly describe how data flows in a radio telescope system, up to the point that telescope data has been combined by the correlator. Figure 2 depicts this data flow between the antennas and the correlator. On the left, antenna signals are digitized by Analog-to-Digital Converters (ADCs), controlled by FPGAs. The FPGAs also filter and packetize the data. The filter separates the signals into disjoint frequency bands, that can each be processed independently by the different GPU correlator machines on the right.

As each digitizer FPGA holds the signals from all frequency bands of one antenna, while a GPU correlator node needs one frequency band of all antennas, the data transport from the FPGAs to the GPU systems forms a left-to-right any-to-any pattern, which is known as the “corner turn”. In other words: each FPGA sends packets to all GPU correlator systems, and each GPU correlator system receives packets from all FPGAs. The corner turn is performed on the network switch in the middle of the figure, which is physically close to the GPU correlator systems.

Depending on the telescope, the FPGAs digitizers and the GPU correlator systems may be any distance between a few meters and thousands of kilometers apart (the distance between the

two outermost antennas is one of the factors that determines the eventual image resolution). We use Ethernet as transportation method, because Ethernet is well supported by both the FPGAs and by the GPU systems. Moreover, Ethernet works over any distance. Often, these Ethernet packets are formatted as UDP/IP packets, so that they can be routed. By design, the data transport is unreliable, as a reliable protocol like TCP would severely complicate the FPGA firmware and requires additional buffering, while in a real-time environment there is generally no time for retransmissions anyway. Also, the post-correlator processing pipeline may discard data for other reasons (in particular, due to Radio Frequency Interference), so the pipeline is well capable of handling missing data. Apart from UDP/IP/Ethernet headers, the packets contain an application-specific header with a timestamp of the precise time that the first sample in the packet was taken, the antenna number, and the frequency band number. The packet payload typically contains a few thousand consecutive (filtered) antenna samples, so that the size of the whole packet does not exceed the jumbo frame limit (9000 bytes), while the header size is small compared to the payload size.

A complicating factor of a correlator application is that we cannot assume that the data from all antennas arrive at the same time in a correlator system. Packets from a thousand kilometer distant antenna may arrive tens or even a hundred milliseconds later than from a nearby antenna. To combine the samples, the input streams from the different antennas must be re-aligned. Therefore, each correlator system maintains a ring buffer in which the input data is buffered, typically for hundreds of milliseconds or a few seconds. For each antenna, a separate ring buffer is used. The ring buffer is selected by the antenna-number value in the packet header, and the location within the ring buffer where samples from the packet payload are stored is determined by the header's timestamp value modulo the ring-buffer size. The ring-buffer data is continuously overwritten by newer data, so there is only a limited amount of time available to process the data. The data also needs to be available in the buffer while it is being transferred to the GPU.

This work focuses on the receipt and processing of the network packets in the GPU systems, on the right in Figure 2. Whereas in the 10 and 40 GbE era UDP/IP packets could be received through the operating system, the interrupt, context switching, and packet copying overheads are too large for 100 Gb/s Ethernet and beyond. Hence, we need a mechanism that bypasses the operating system in the critical receive path. Others tried *ibverbs* to bypass the operating system, e.g., in the SPEAD2 packet-handling library [6] or in an experimental setup [7], but the receive performance that could be obtained with it in practice, fell 10–30% short of the used Ethernet line rates (200 and 400 Gb/s, respectively). As we strive to achieve line speeds from *multiple* network interfaces, we chose for the Data Plane Development Kit (DPDK), also because of its recently added support for GPUs.

DPDK is a toolkit that allows an application to take full control over a network interface, bypassing the OS. The main functions are the functions that take care of receiving and sending Ethernet packets, and the ones that manage packet buffers in memory pools. Any network protocol on top of Ethernet also has to be implemented in user space. For simple protocols like UDP/IP, the application will likely implement the protocol stack itself, but for complex protocols like TCP/IP, it is probably more convenient to use an open-source user-level library like F-Stack [8]. As a DPDK application can send and receive any Ethernet packet on a network, which is a severe security threat, DPDK applications run with an elevated privilege level (as superuser, or with some specific capabilities). The toolkit is supported by all major NIC vendors, but the GPUdev extension currently only works on NVIDIA NICs and NVIDIA GPUs. We elaborate on the use of DPDK in the next section.

2.3 Implementation

Figure 3: Copy behavior of the different implementations.

We implemented three correlator variants. Each of them uses DPDK, but the data paths are different. Figure 3a depicts how the most straightforward implementation of a GPU correlator works: the packets are received in DPDK packet buffers, the packet data is copied into the ring buffers in CPU memory, and after some time, when all data for a particular time interval has arrived (or should have arrived), the section of ring-buffer data for that time interval is copied to GPU memory, for each antenna. Subsequently, the GPU processes the data. We call this the *2-copy* variant, as receiving data from the NIC is generally not counted as a “copy” action.

The second variant does not have the ring buffers in CPU memory, but in GPU memory (see Figure 3b). Here, the packets are still received in DPDK packet buffers, but their contents are copied into the GPU ring buffers. We call this the *1-copy* variant. Alternatively, we could have stored the ring buffers in CPU memory and let the GPU channel filter kernel read the ring buffer contents through unified memory, but despite the use of NVLink, this makes the channel filter kernel prohibitively slow, so we do not further consider this alternative.

The third variant, the *0-copy* variant, works quite differently (see Figure 3c). Rather than implementing the ring buffer as a flat memory buffer, we use a giant amount of DPDK packet buffers as “ring buffer”, and process the data at a later moment directly from the packet buffers. For this, we use the recently added GPU support in DPDK, *GPUdev* [5], that allows allocating packet buffers in GPU memory. DPDK also allows splitting packets, and receive packet fragments in different memory pools. We allocate one memory pool in CPU memory and another memory pool in GPU memory, and split incoming packets so that each packet header (56 bytes) is received in CPU memory, and the associated packet payload (8192 bytes) is received in GPU memory. Important to note is that 99.3% of the packet data is directly DMAed from the NIC into GPU memory, bypassing CPU memory. The packet headers contain the timestamps and antenna numbers, that determine the location in the ring buffer. The timestamps and antenna numbers are inspected by the CPU, and a pointer to the packet payload (in GPU memory) is placed in the ring buffer. The ring buffers thus contains pointers to packet payloads instead of the samples themselves. After all packets from a certain time interval should have arrived, the CPU copies the ring buffer payload pointers to the GPU, and launches the filter and correlator kernels that we describe in Section 2.3.1.

Even though we use almost 74 GB (77%) of the GPU memory for buffering packet payloads, the buffer fills up quickly at high data rates. At the maximum data rate of 1.2 Tb/s, the 9.4-million entry packet buffer is completely filled after only 0.52 seconds. The GPU processes blocks of 18 GB of data (one quarter of the ring buffer size), which corresponds to 0.13 seconds at the highest data rates, so that the remainder of the ring buffer is used to receive new packets, while there is also sufficient time to overcome the packet arrival time differences from the different

antennas.

At first, using large amounts of GPU memory with GPUdev did not work well. During program initialization, the GPU memory is registered by DPDK to make it accessible to the NICs, but registering a few gigabytes of GPU memory was prohibitively slow (taking hours), and was exponentially slower for even larger sizes. We fixed this in DPDK's mlx5 driver, by sorting a list of segments only once instead of for each added segment [9]. Alternatively, one can workaround the slow initialization by specifying a wrong GPU page size: claiming that the GPU pages size is 2 MB instead of 64 GB reduces the total initialization time to seconds.

All variants support multiple receive queues per NIC; this is an adjustable parameter. Each receive queue is associated with one CPU thread that continuously polls the queue for incoming packets. By dividing the streams from the antennas over more and more receive queues, the load on each CPU core can be reduced.

As all cores and CPU memory in the Grace CPU are in the same NUMA domain, there is no need to bind threads to specific cores. Yet we distinguish between threads that poll a NIC receive queue and threads that do not; the polling threads make as few system calls as possible (to not stop receiving packets for an extended period of time), while (blocking) system calls are performed by the latter group of threads.

DPDK's per-core memory pool cache plays a crucial role in obtaining good performance. This is a 512-entry per-core cache where a core can quickly allocate and deallocate packets from, instead of using the much slower shared pool. We found that, no matter how many cores are used, data rates beyond 800 Gb/s are impossible without effective use of the memory pool cache. This limits the freedom in application design choices. First, one cannot receive a packet by one core, hand it over another core that manages the GPU, and let the GPU-managing core deallocate the packet when the GPU is ready, because the receiving core would always encounter an empty cache and the deallocating core a full cache. Second, one cannot deallocate large amounts of packets in one go (even though a burst deallocation function is available). Instead, after a packet has been processed, we defer packet deallocation, so that every time a new packet is received, another unused packet is deallocated. This keeps the cache usually in a partially filled state.

It is worth noting that NVIDIA Holoscan [10] is a framework that supports implementing applications for real-time sensor processing on GPUs, but this framework was not yet available when we started this study. As Holoscan is built on top of DPDK, we expect similar performance.

2.3.1 GPU processing

Figure 4: Simplified view of the GPU processing pipeline.

Although a comprehensive study of the GPU kernels is outside the scope of this study, we briefly describe the signal-processing operations performed by the GPU. The GPU performs three major tasks: it handles the input packets (this only applies to the 0-copy variant), and subsequently channelizes and correlates the signals (see Figure 4). The last two tasks are standard signal-processing operations that basically every (GPU) correlator performs.

Even though packet handling and channel filtering are depicted as two operations, they are performed by the same GPU kernel. The channel filter comes from a newly developed GPU

library, that combines a PolyPhase Filter Bank (FIR filters and FFT), delay compensation (optional), bandpass correction (optional), and a memory transpose in a single GPU kernel. This "radio block" is described in Deliverable D4.4. All these operations are fused in a single kernel, to reduce the number of GPU memory accesses. To create efficient code, the library compiles the GPU code at run time, when the number of antennas, frequency channels, etc. are known. We use the runtime compilation property also to provide the library with custom GPU code that reads input data from DPDK packet payloads, rather than a flat memory buffer. This is a nice separation of responsibilities: the filter library itself is oblivious of DPDK, yet the GPU channel filter kernel is heavily involved in processing the DPDK packets.

The second GPU kernel is a correlator kernel that combines the antenna data by pairwise multiplication and integration of the filtered antenna samples. This kernel comes from the *Tensor-Core Correlator* library [11], that performs these operations on tensor cores. It is the fastest (GPU) correlator to date. This "radio block" is also described in Deliverable D4.4.

Once the data from all antennas should have arrived in the ring buffers (possibly with a time offset), the GPU processes blocks of 18 GB of data; a quarter of the ring buffer size. Consecutive blocks are slightly overlapping, as the FIR filters in the channelizer are in fact convolutions that need some historical data from the previous block. This complicates the implementation. Due to the large data blocks on which the GPU operates, the kernel launch overhead is negligible. Yet, the kernels are launched by a different thread than the CPU threads that receive DPDK packets, as the kernel launches may involve (blocking) system calls.

We considered using a persistent GPU kernel that would poll for new incoming packets, and immediately process (channelize) new packet data. The advantage of that would be that the amount of packet buffers could be kept small, decreasing the DPDK overhead. On the other hand, it may increase the energy use, as it keeps the GPU busy at all times, even if there is no new data to process. Unfortunately, a persistent kernel is difficult to implement in this case, for several reasons. In particular, the realignment in time of the channelized data prior to correlation (which requires some sort of ring buffer as well), but also the missing support for persistent kernels in the filter library, the internal state that a filter must maintain, the deallocation of processed packets, and CPU-GPU synchronization all add to the complexity. Therefore, we refrained from using a persistent kernel.

2.3.2 Correlator output

In this study, we do not specifically optimize for high output data rates, as the output data rate of a correlator is typically (much) lower than the input data rate. If the output is written to file, we use the new cuFile library from the CUDA toolkit to write data directly from GPU memory to file. Alternatively, the data can be sent over a TCP connection to an external system. For simplicity, we do this via the operating system (and another virtual instance of one of the NICs), which works fine for speeds up to roughly 50 Gb/s. If the output data rate requirements for a specific instrument setup would exceed this, the output data path should also be optimized (either through DPDK, or some RDMA protocol), but at such high output data rates, the biggest challenges would not be in the correlator itself, but in the post-correlator processing pipeline.

2.4 Performance

In this section, we analyze the application and DPDK performance on the CPU and GPU. Although in reality antenna data are digitized and packetized by FPGAs near the individual antennas, in this experimental setup we use a CPU-based packet generator that mimics the FPGA behavior, for practical reasons. We only evaluate the performance of a single GPU correlator system, as

multi-GPU correlator systems operate independently of each other, since they each process a different frequency band, so multi-GPU scaling is trivial. The corner turn does *not* scale trivially, and can impose high packet-switching requirements on the switch, but this is outside the scope of this demonstration.

The measurements were performed on two QCT S74G-2U Grace Hopper systems with 96 GB HBM3 and 480 GB LPDDR5 memory (one for the packet generator, the other one for the GPU correlator), using a patched version of DPDK 24.03 (see Section 2.3) and linux kernel 6.5.0-1024-nvidia-64k. For availability reasons, we use a mixture of 400 GbE and dual-port 200 GbE ConnectX-7 NICs, for a total of 1200 Gb/s per system (in each direction). To simplify the software, we split the 400 GbE NICs into two virtual 200 GbE NICs, so that the software does not need to distinguish between different link speeds. In practice, we saw that a single 400 GbE link and two bundled 200 GbE links behaved similarly. Ssh connections are routed via a separate USB-Ethernet dongle, to not interfere with the high-speed network interfaces. Unless stated otherwise, 12 (out of 72 available) CPU cores are used to poll the NICs and insert the packets in the circular buffer. We simulate 72 antennas, a fairly typical amount of antennas for a radio telescope.

Figure 5: Achieved input network bandwidth (without packet loss).

We seek for the largest amount of data that a Grace Hopper system could receive and process in real time, without packet loss. Figure 5 shows the obtained network bandwidth, for each of the three variants. The 2-copy variant runs up to 309 Gb/s without packet loss. The 1-copy variant works best with 24 cores, and achieves a data rate of 670 Gb/s. The 2-copy and 1-copy variants can actually process higher data rates, but start to drop packets then, something that we wish to avoid. Only the 0-copy variant is able to process packets at 1.2 Tb/s. This means that the application is still limited by network bandwidth, but this bandwidth is six times higher than what was possible with previous-generation GPUs. And as we will see later, the GPU would not be able to handle a much higher data rate, so the GPU compute power and I/O capabilities are fairly in balance.

Figure 6 shows the actual CPU memory bandwidth use, which is a scarce resource for the 2-copy and 1-copy variants. Unfortunately, the CPU memory bandwidth use cannot be measured directly with the Grace CPU performance counters. The *Grace Performance Tuning Guide* [12]

Figure 6: CPU memory bandwidth use.

explains how to measure this, but we found that the CPU memory bandwidth use due to PCIe and NVLink DMA transfers is not included then, so we measured these separately, and added them. The memory bandwidth use as shown in the figure is thus a lower bound; we cannot rule out that there is memory traffic for reasons we are unaware of.

From the figure, we see that the 2-copy and 1-copy variants would never scale to 1.2 Tb/s, as their extrapolated graphs exceed the memory bandwidth that is available. A separate benchmark measured the best-case memory bandwidth at 340 GB/s, which is consistent with what is reported in the Tuning Guide [12]. Yet, we see that the 2-copy and 1-copy variants do not get close to the 340 GB/s bandwidth use as they start losing packets; this already happens around 200 GB/s. For the 2-copy variant, this is mostly due to the irregular CPU-to-GPU transfers: due to the high NVLink link speed, these transfers can claim all the available CPU memory bandwidth, leaving insufficient memory bandwidth for packet receipt. The 1-copy variant does not suffer from this, still the memory access pattern is not optimal to reach full bandwidth without packet loss.

In fact, the 0-copy variant is the only variant that does not suffer from insufficient CPU memory bandwidth; the figure shows that its actual memory bandwidth use is low. In the remainder of this section, we only consider the 0-copy variant.

Note that, unlike CPU memory bandwidth, GPU memory bandwidth is amply available; the 150 GB/s that is needed to store packet payloads, is only a small fraction of the 3.5 TB/s that is available.

2.4.1 Energy efficiency

A well-known technique to improve the energy efficiency of a GPU (and many other processors) is to run the application at a reduced the clock frequency [13]. As the GPU idles for 23% of the time at the default (and highest supported) clock frequency, there is room to reduce the clock speed, up to the point that it just does not lose real-time behavior (see Figure 7). This way, we can reduce the energy consumption already by 96 Watt.

Similarly, we can reduce the CPU clock frequency (see Figure 8). Note that, unlike the GPU

Figure 7: GPU performance and energy efficiency. On the left: the time spent in the different kernels, as a function of clock frequency (note that the DPDK packet handling is in fact part of the filter kernel, but its execution time is shown separately). On the right: the energy use.

Figure 8: CPU performance and energy efficiency. On the left: the time spent in DPDK and in the application code, as a function of clock frequency. On the right: the energy use.

kernels, the packet-handling CPU cores never idle but keep on polling the NICs to check if new packets have arrived. When using only 6 CPU cores to handle the incoming packets, there is hardly any room to reduce the clock frequency without packet loss. However, if we increase the number of polling cores to 12, we can decrease the clock frequency all the way down to 1.8 GHz, without observing packet loss. This way, we can decrease the CPU power from 119 Watt (with 6 fast-running cores) to 69 Watt (with 12 slow-running cores). We see no additional benefit from increasing the number of polling cores to 18, because the clock speed cannot be reduced any further without packet loss.

2.5 Discussion

So far, we learned that the DPDK approach, and in particular its recent support to receive packet payloads in GPU memory, yield extremely high data rates on streaming data, and good application performance. However, there are some drawbacks to this approach. First, the DPDK model provides no method to control *where* packet payloads are received in GPU memory. As a result, the GPU spends 22%–27% of the time collecting the input data from the scattered packet payloads: looking up an input sample requires an extra pointer indirection, and GPUs have no huge page support to reduce the amount of TLB misses. Second, splitting packets increases

DPDK's internal CPU overhead; the header and payload buffers are allocated and deallocated from separately managed memory pools.

We tried receiving the full packet (header and payload) in GPU memory. As, in this case, the relevant metadata (timestamp, antenna number) are in GPU memory, either the CPU needs to retrieve this data from GPU memory so that it can place the packet in the circular buffer, or the GPU itself should fully handle the packet and maintain the circular buffer itself. Unfortunately, for the former approach, the DPDK toolkit refused to register unified (managed) memory, so that the memory would have been accessible by the NIC, CPU, and GPU. And the latter approach is difficult to implement. For example, when the GPU finished processing a packet, it cannot return the packet fragments to the header and payload pools and should leave this to the CPU, but then it is difficult to make efficient use of DPDK's mbuf cache, which is crucial for performance.

Finally, the presented 0-copy method is difficult to integrate into existing GPU correlator applications, due to the different way in which input data is stored, the different roles of CPU threads, and the prohibitive costs of thread synchronization for every received packet. The application that we use for this demonstration, was written from scratch (except for the GPU kernels) so that DPDK could be properly integrated.

On the other hand, we have not seen any competing approach that yields such high data rates, and given the enormous increase in achieved data rates, we consider the DPDK and GPUdev solution as a major step forward.

2.6 Conclusions

The work presented in this sections demonstrates that, through a combination of hardware and software innovations, an enormous increase in network packet processing data rates has been achieved. The Grace Hopper architecture eliminates the PCIe bandwidth limitation, the Data Plane Development Kit (DPDK) removed the operating system overhead of receiving network packets, DPDK's recent support for GPUs allowed receiving packet data directly from the network interface into GPU memory, and the GPU application processes network packet payloads. Without these innovations, handling packets at 100 or 200 Gb/s was already difficult, but we demonstrate that 1.2 Tb/s is possible, with a reasonable balance between GPU compute performance and I/O capabilities. The performance analysis shows that the CPU and GPU overheads from handling the network packets is noticeable but not prohibitive. We also showed that tuning clock frequencies led to a 145 Watt reduction in energy use, without reducing overall performance. Future work targets methods that reduce the CPU and GPU overheads, but the data rate cannot be improved any further.

3 RDMA

The RDMA packetiser IP is designed as part of the RADIOBLOCKS project, it enables sending data over the RoCEv2 protocol. Specifically using the RDMA write variant. In contrast to the DPDK implementation which adapts the software stack on the receiving host while using standard UDP protocol, RoCEv2 is an additional protocol encapsulated in the UDP protocol and on the receiving host side leveraging the hardware acceleration of NICs that support RoCEv2.

RoCEv2 is RDMA over Converged Ethernet version 2 protocol. In essence it enables RDMA (Remote Direct Memory Access) over standard TCP/UDP IP networks instead of the default transport layer which is infiniband. The main benefit of using RDMA based data transfer in our applications is that the CPU at the receiving end does not have to process each incoming packet. This is because the network interface recognizes the protocol and is able to directly transfer the data to the final memory location without intervention needed from the CPU. Therefore RDMA / RoCEv2 removes the CPU bottleneck for high bandwidth data transport.

The purpose of the RDMA packetiser IP is to enable RDMA write actions from FPGA to a CPU or GPU. The RDMA write variant is chosen as it can be transported over UDP and the data can be processed without CPU involvement on the receiving end [1].

3.1 RDMA packetiser IP design

The RDMA packetiser IP prepends the RoCEv2 header to an incoming data packet and appends the RDMA ICRC checksum. An external component is used "as is" to compute and append the ICRC checksum, this component cannot handle the ETH part of the header. Therefore, the ETH header is prepended after the ICRC checksum is appended. See figure 9. Note that some names of the blocks in the diagram are in bold, these are newly designed functions while the remaining blocks are existing IP. The existing IP can be found in the ASTRON HDL repository [14].

Figure 9: RDMA packetiser IP block design

3.1.1 RDMA packetiser assemble header

The RDMA packetiser assemble header component assembles the RDMA header to prepend and prepends it to the incoming data stream. The RDMA Write protocol has four possible headers depending on the amount of packets in a message and the packet index. The four variants are

denoted as "first", "mid", "last", and "wo". These contain different sets of sub-headers which is explained in Table 2. This selection process is performed by a state machine that controls a dp_demux / dp_mux. The header is prepended by the new eth_ip_offload component. In order to prevent four MM interfaces for each header variant, an extra dp_offload_tx_v3 is used only for MM (no SOSI output) in which the header is configured. The correct parts of the header is then selected by a process that sets the header fields input on each of the eth_ip_offloads. See Figure 10.

Header variant	Consists of	Total packets in message	packet position in message	immediate data is enabled	Extra condition
first	IP + UDP + BTH + RETH	> = 1	first	don't care	Only "first" if conditions for "wo" are not met.
mid	IP + UDP + BTH	> 1	not first	don't care	Only "mid" if conditions for "last" are not met.
last	IP + UDP + BTH + Immediate_data	> 1	last	true	None
wo	IP + UDP + BTH + RETH + Immediate_data	1	first (only one)	true	None

Table 2: RDMA Write header variants

3.1.2 RDMA header state machine

A state machine is used to select the correct RDMA write header. In addition it sets the "opcode" and the "virtual_address" fields of the header. The diagram in Figure 3 shows the working of the state machine. Notice that the state machine performs the tasks below in addition to what is described in the diagram.

- The state machine is executed on snk_in.sop = '1' only.
- The p_cnt value is increased by one every execution (every snk_in.sop).
- When the opcode is set, the corresponding UDP/IP total length header fields are also set at the same time. The "block_len" input signal is used in determining these values.
- When the opcode is set, sel_ctrl is also set according to Table 3.

The following values used by the state machine are MM controlled:

- nof_packets_in_msg
- dma_len

Figure 10: RDMA packetiser assemble header block design

opcode	sel_ctrl
write_first	0
write_only	0
write_middle	1
write_last	1
write_last_imm	2
write_only_imm	3

Table 3: sel_ctrl selection

- start_address
- nof_msg
- use_immediate

3.1.3 field_select_subset process

The field_select_subset is a new function in the common_field package to select a subset of a vector that corresponds to a field array. This is useful in the RDMA packetiser to select the necessary content for the four header variants as previously described in Table 2. The function takes the t_common_field_arr that describes the desired field array, the t_common_field_arr of the larger field array and the std_logic_vector that corresponds with the larger field array. The function returns the std_logic_vector that corresponds to the desired common_field_arr.

RDMA header state machine

Figure 11: RDMA header state machine diagram

3.1.4 eth_ip_offload component

The eth_ip_offload consists of dp_offload_tx_v3 followed by eth_ip_checksum.

3.1.5 append_crc_dp_wrapper component

A wrapper around the icrc checksum computation originating from Willam Kamp ¹ for a study ² in the SKA project. The component calculates a crc32 value based on the whole packet and an additional pseudo header according the the RDMA specification, this is described very well in [15]. The resulting checksum is appended to the incoming data stream. It expects an input stream that contains the IP/UDP header followed by the RDMA header and the data. Notice that it does not expect the ETH header.

3.2 RDMA packetiser IP simulation

3.2.1 Testbench

The testbench is written in Python using the cocotb framework to easily allow for an extensive and thorough verification. It sends data packets to the input sisi and expects correctly formatted RoCEv2 packets at the output sisi. The testbench performs the following actions

¹ Re-used with permission from William Kamp, High Performance Computing Research Lab, AUT
² <https://gitlab.com/ska-telescope/rdma-data-transport>

- Write and read/verify the rdma_packetiser configuration and header values over MM.
- Send a set of DP packets containing just data (no headers).
- Verify the output DP packets, the following parts of the packet is verified:
 - Packet header (ETH + IP + UDP + RDMA).
 - Packet payload (should be identical to the input data).
 - RDMA icrc value.

3.2.2 Simulation results

The simulation results include a printout of the headers detected in the Ethernet packet using the Python Scapy library. These results show that the packets are correctly identified as RocEv2 packets, unfortunately Scapy only supports the BTH header of the RocEv2 protocol and does not support the RETH and Immdiate data headers. The RETH + Imm. Data header are verified manually without the use of Scapy.

The partial wave window in figure 12 shows how the state machine cycles through the three different states correctly (first, middle, last).

Figure 12: RDMA packetiser simulation wave window.

3.3 Conclusion

The work presented in this section demonstrates an efficient solution for enabling high-performance data transfers using the RoCEv2 protocol. Implementing the RDMA Write variant, the IP is able to bypass traditional CPU involvement during data reception, therefore eliminating bottlenecks and facilitating direct memory access in the target device. The modular design approach, which includes components for header assembly, CRC calculation, and Ethernet/IP offloading, ensures a flexible and scalable architecture. The integration of an RDMA header state machine further enhances functionality by dynamically selecting the appropriate header configuration for various packet types. The verification strategy using the cocotb framework has validated the correct assembly of packets, confirming compliance with the RoCEv2 standard. Despite some limitations with Scapy support for RETH and immediate data headers, manual verification has confirmed the correctness of these header structures, reinforcing the robustness of the design. This RDMA packetiser IP offers a reliable and scalable building block for high-bandwidth applications, contributing to efficient data transport solutions in modern FPGA-based systems.

4 RDMA versus DPDK, and future prospects of software-based methods

In chapter 2, we presented our implementation with DPDK, which demonstrates a significant increase in network packet processing data rates through the integration of innovative hardware and software solutions. The elimination of PCIe bandwidth limitations, combined with the removal of operating system overhead through DPDK, and the direct transfer of packet data from the network interface to GPU memory, enabled the development of a high-performance network processing system.

In chapter 3, we described our implementation of RDMA (RoCE v2), where the FPGA could potentially write data directly to a predefined location within a GPU ring buffer. This method is expected to be more energy efficient than software based approaches, such as DPDK, as it eliminates the need for CPU intervention and allows for direct data transfer into GPU memory. Furthermore, the CPU overhead associated with data processing is anticipated to be significantly reduced. However, the development of FPGA firmware for a complex protocol like RoCE is a time-consuming process, the work included in this report has been verified in simulation, but not yet in real hardware.

Although a hardware based approach such as our RoCE implementation could lead to reduced resource usage of the CPU on the receiving system, we currently favor software based approaches due to the lower complexity of the implementation while still achieving a very high data transport bandwidth. The implementation with DPDK has enabled the achievement of unprecedented data rates of 1.2 Tb/s, while maintaining a reasonable balance between compute performance and I/O capabilities. Moreover, we think that the CPU and GPU overhead, for software based approaches, could be further reduced if the payload of the network packets would have been received at the "right" place in a flat ring buffer in GPU memory, so that the GPU does not have to look up the location of a payload buffer, and the CPU does not need to spend time managing a huge mbuf pool.

In the remainder of this project, we plan to explore the NVIDIA DOCA toolkit [16], an alternative to DPDK GPUdev, to investigate if we can reduce the CPU and GPU overheads, and simplify programming. DOCA is a collection of SDKs that provide low-level access to NVIDIA ConnectX and BlueField network interfaces. Each of these SDKs has its own properties and supported features; some of them have support for (NVIDIA) GPUs. We consider the following SDKs:

- *DOCA Ethernet* allows packet receipt directly into GPU memory (like DPDK GPUdev), but DOCA Ethernet receives them in a circular buffer rather than a memory pool, so that consecutive packets are received one after another in GPU memory. This method should lead to lower CPU overhead, but it is unclear if we can efficiently handle nonconsecutive timestamps due to missing packets with this SDK.
- *DOCA GPUNetIO* is another SDK that allows the GPU (rather than the CPU) to control the NIC. As far as we understand, it would reduce the CPU overhead but not the GPU overhead.
- *DOCA DPA* or the DOCA driver layer (*DOCA FlexIO*) seem the most promising SDKs. These SDKs allow programming the processor cores on the network interface (the Data Path Accelerator, DPA) with application-specific code. This should allow us to inspect the headers of incoming packets on the network interface itself, and transfer the packet's payload directly to the right location in a ring buffer in GPU memory, based on the timestamp, antenna number, and frequency band that are stored in the header, If this works, we would fully eliminate the CPU and GPU overheads.

Some of these SDKs are new, may not be fully stable, have limited documentation, and come with few example programs. It shows that network interface and GPU integration is a rapidly evolving research area. Fortunately, NVIDIA is willing to help us, and is fast in responding to the questions we have.

5 FPGA Hardware

In this chapter, we present the design, considerations and implementation of the FPGA-based hardware solution used for the prototype described in Section 7. This solution leverages the Intel Agilex 7 SoC-FPGA, integrated within the iWave development kit, to support high-performance data transfers and enable efficient handling of 200GbE and 400GbE protocols.

Section 5.1 provides detailed information about the development platform. Section 5.2 explains the transceiver architecture and its constraints.

5.1 iWave development kit

The iwave development kit is composed by two elements, the iWave SOM (System On Module) iW-RainboW-G43M board and the iWave carrier board iW-RainboW-G43D. The SOM board implements the Intel Agilex 7 SoC-FPGA and all the peripherals needed for the FPGA chip to work. The carrier board implements different interfaces to explore and test the Agilex 7 SoC-FPGA chip.

Figure 13 shows the functional block diagram of the selected iWave SOM iW-RainboW-G43M board and Figure 14 shows the functional block diagram of the iWave carrier iW-RainboW-G43D board.

Figure 13: iWave iWave SOM iW-RainboW-G43M board block diagram

The FPGA selection was strongly driven by the transceiver requirements related to the input and output interfaces for the ALMA case, respectively from the digitizer (6 bits, 40GSps, demux by 4) and to the correlator (400 GbE or 2x200GbE). For one ADC (one front-end datapath), 24 * 10G NRZ and 8 * 58G (or 4 * 116G) PAM4 transceivers are required.

Figure 14: iWave iW-RainboW-G43D carrier board block diagram

This iWave development kit supports the following features:

• **HPS Interface Features**

- Gigabit Ethernet through RJ45 x 1
- USB2.0 OTG through Type C connector x 1
- Debug UART through Type C connector x 1

- **FPGA Interface Features**

- PCIe16 Connector x 1
- QSFP Stacked Connector (QSFP112 + QSFP) x 2
- FMC+ High Pin Count (HPC) Connector 1
 - * 24 High Speed Transceivers
 - * 6 Transceiver Reference Clock (M2C)
 - * Up to 36 LVDS IOs
 - * Up to 4 Single Ended (SE) IOs
 - * 7 Clock Input Capable LVDS/SE pins
- FMC+ High Pin Count (HPC) Connector 2
 - * 12 High Speed Transceivers
 - * 3 Transceiver Reference Clock (M2C)
 - * Up to 34 LVDS IOs
 - * Up to 8 Single Ended (SE) IOs
 - * 7 Clock Input Capable LVDS/SE pins
- FMC+ High Pin Count (HPC) Connector 3
 - * Up to 36 LVDS IOs
 - * Up to 21 Single Ended (SE) IOs
 - * 6 Clock Input Capable LVDS/SE pins
- PMOD Connectors x 1

- **Additional Features**

- Clock Synthesizers/Generators x 4
- I2C Expander x 1
- JTAG Connector x 1
- Power ON/OFF DIP Switch x 1
- Reset Pushbutton Switch x 1

The utilization of the iWave development kit, particularly the iW-RainboW-G43D carrier board, imposes a limitation on interfacing the ADC component, as it is restricted to the FMC+ connector 1, which supports up to 24 transceiver lanes. Due to the routing constraints of the remaining transceiver lanes on the Agilex 7 chip, this development kit only allows for the implementation of a single ADC interface. As a result, the prototype is constrained to supporting only one front-end datapath.

5.2 Agilex 7 F-Tile High-Speed Transceivers

The Agilex 7 chip integrates high-speed transceivers within F-Tiles, as illustrated in Figure 15.

Each F-Tile consists of 16 FGT transceivers (organized into 4 Quads) and 4 FHT transceivers, with each transceiver corresponding to a single PMA lane. The FGT and FHT transceivers support distinct data rates, which are detailed in Figure 16.

Additionally, each F-Tile incorporates 24 Embedded Multi-Die Interconnect Bridges (EMIB) to interface with the FPGA fabric. Each EMIB provides a maximum bandwidth of 32 Gbps, necessitating two EMIBs for 58G operation and four EMIBs for 116G operation.

Furthermore, each F-Tile supports three types of hard IP for data transport: 400G Hard IP, 200G Hard IP, and PCIe Hard IP. The utilization of each Hard IP is subject to specific constraints regarding the associated transceivers and EMIB resources.

Figure 15: Agilix 7 F-tiles architecture

Data rate range	<p>FHT:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 24-29 Gbps NRZ 48-58 Gbps NRZ and PAM4 96-116 Gbps PAM4 <p>FGT:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1-32 Gbps NRZ 20-58.125 PAM4
-----------------	---

Figure 16: FGT and FHT data rates

In our case, the architecture is constrained by the specific implementation of the chip provided by the iWave development kit, limiting the available options to the use of FHT transceivers exclusively for the 200/400GbE protocols. The only viable approach to leverage these FHT transceivers for the targeted protocols is to implement a 400G Hard IP, which supports both 200GbE and 400GbE protocols.

For the RadioBlocks D4.3 prototype, the primary objective is to implement the 400G Hard

IP to support the 200GbE protocol using four FHT 58G transceivers in 200G-4 Ethernet mode. Subsequently, the goal is to extend this implementation by utilizing the 400G Hard IP to support the 400GbE protocol over four FHT 116G transceivers in 400G-4 Ethernet mode.

6 FPGA Firmware

In this chapter, we present the design and implementation of the firmware used for the prototype demonstrator, further elaborated in Section 7. This section focuses on handling high-speed data flow, implementing the 200GbE and 400GbE protocols, and incorporating half-band filters.

Section 6.1 provides detailed information about the architecture of the F-Tile Ethernet Intel® FPGA Hard IP. Section 6.2 explains the necessity of half-band filters in the firmware and describes the models used.

6.1 F-Tile Ethernet Intel® FPGA Hard IP

The 200G or 400G over Ethernet links are implemented using the F-Tile Ethernet Intel® FPGA Hard IP. Figure 17 displays the F-Tile Ethernet Intel® FPGA Hard IP core block diagram, showing significant blocks and connections.

It consists of synthesizable soft-logic and the hardened IP core block. Each F-Tile Ethernet Intel® FPGA Hard IP core consists of a single Ethernet port, configurable for 10GE, 25GE, 40GE, 50GE, 100GE, 200GE, or 400GE data rate. The same implementation applies to all supported data rate IP options.

Figure 17: F-Tile Ethernet Intel® FPGA Hard IP Block Diagram

Figure 18 shows the F-Tile Ethernet Intel FPGA Hard IP design example which include the following components:

- F-Tile Ethernet Intel FPGA Hard IP : Generated IP core.

- F-Tile Reference and System PLL Clocks Intel® FPGA IP : Instantiated reference clock and system PLL clock IP.
- Packet Client: Consists of a packet generator, a packet checker and a loopback client. The Packet Client generates various ROM-based traffic patterns for MAC mode and can loop-back the RX and TX client side.
- Avalon® memory-mapped interface Decoder: Decodes the Avalon® memory-mapped interface address to Hardware IP Top.

Figure 18: Design Example Block Diagram

6.2 Half-band filters

The digitizer used for this application generates a very high data rate, with 6 bits and a sampling rate of 40 GSps, resulting in a data rate of 240 Gbps. While the network interface card used for this first demo is based on 2 x 200 GbE ports. To ensure that the data rate does not exceed the limit of 200 GbE network protocol, a half band filter has been developed. The digitized signal is split into two sub-bands: a high frequency band (10 to 20 GHz) and a low frequency band (0 to 10 GHz), producing 8 bits data sampled at 20 GSps (resulting in a data rate of 160 Gbps) for each sub-band.

A spectral translation method is applied to the signal prior to filtering. This technique involves spectrally shifting the signal so that the filter transition bands align with the desired frequency ranges. A low-pass FIR filter designed using MATLAB's Filter Designer was used. This filter has a cutoff frequency of 4 GHz and a transition band extending up to 5 GHz. Its order, determined by the tool, is 102. To extract the high-frequency band from 10 to 20 GHz, the signal was shifted down by 14 GHz prior to filtering. Similarly, for the low-frequency band from 0 to 10 GHz, the signal was shifted down by 6 GHz prior to filtering. After the spectral decomposition, downsampling was applied by selecting every other sample for each band, reducing the data rate by a factor of 2, thus reaching a sampling rate of 20 GSps.

The design has been validated with a noise signal covering the entire frequency range from 0 to 20 GHz, to which sinewaves at specific frequencies were added [1 GHz, 5 GHz, 9 GHz, 12 GHz, 18 GHz, 19 GHz]. As we can see in Figure 19 the sinewaves are well placed in their respective bands: between 2 and 10 GHz for the low frequency band; between 10 and 18 GHz for the high frequency band.

Figure 19: Half band filter model

The filter coefficients have to be quantized to fixed-point prior to FPGA implementation. And it is essential to compare the simulation results before and after quantization. This analysis was performed by quantizing the filter coefficients to 16 bits. Figure 20 shows that there is no significant change to the signal to noise ratio after quantization.

Figure 20: Quantization effects

7 High-Speed Data Transport Prototype

7.1 System Demonstration Setup

The high-speed data transport prototype demonstration setup is illustrated in Figure 21. This demonstration setup includes only one front-end data chain due to the limitation of the iWave carrier board to implement transceiver interfaces for handling two front-ends.

The setup consists of the following components:

- **CW & WGN Generator:** Continuous wave (CW) and white Gaussian noise (WGN) generators are employed to emulate the data signal generated by the receivers (antennas).
- **RF Chain:** The radio frequency (RF) chain implements amplifiers and filters, designed to process the analog signal and ensure it meets the electrical characteristics required by the digitizer.
- **125 MHz Reference Clock:** A 125 MHz reference clock provides the timing reference for the entire system.
- **20 GHz Sampling Clock:** A 20 GHz sampling clock, derived from the 125 MHz reference clock, serves as the sampling clock for the digitizer.
- **Digitizer Prototype:** The digitizer prototype is a custom-designed board equipped with the M8130Y ADC component, capable of digitizing signals at 40 GSps.
- **iWave Development Kit:** The iWave development kit consists of two main components:
 - SOM Board: Integrates the Intel Agilex 7 I-series FPGA chip.
 - Carrier Board: Provides the necessary interfaces for utilizing the FPGA.

This development kit captures digitized samples from the digitizer prototype board using high-speed transceivers and implements the 200GbE/400GbE IPs to transmit data to the GPU correlator.

- **GPU Correlator:** The GPU correlator employs the DPDK protocol and executes correlation code for further processing.
- **External Computer:** An external computer hosts test software to control and monitor the entire system demonstration setup.

Figure 21: System demonstration setup for the High-speed data transport prototype diagram

Figure 22 shows the current prototype. As seen in the picture, since the firmware for the iWave development kit is still in the final stages of development, the kit is not yet connected to the digitization chain. Instead, it has been replaced by an older development kit featuring a Stratix 10 GX FPGA, which is running preliminary firmware that is capable of collecting samples from the digitizer.

Figure 22: High-speed data transport prototype picture

7.2 Prototype development status and measurements

7.2.1 FPGA Hardware

iWave Development Kit Due to the limitations of the selected iWave carrier board, the current demonstration is restricted to the use of a single 200G Ethernet Hard IP. Once the new custom carrier board, currently under manufacturing, will be received, the implementation will be upgraded to support 400G Ethernet.

Agilex 7 F-Tile High-Speed Transceivers Agilex 7 F-Tile High-Speed Transceivers have been implemented on the chip using a custom design. The transceivers were tested using the Intel Transceiver Toolkit, an Intel Quartus Prime plugin that enables the control and monitoring of on-board transceivers via a JTAG link.

Figure 23 presents the results of the transceiver toolkit test. This test validates the functionality of an internal transceiver loopback. It is important to note that this design does not include an Ethernet IP, as the test focuses only on the transceivers' performance.

This test validates the transceiver implementation by confirming the absence of bit errors.

Figure 23: Intel Transceiver Toolkit test results

7.2.2 FPGA Firmware

Prototype Firmware Design The prototype firmware design is based on the ALMA WSU WIFP firmware. This design incorporates sample reception as input, logic-based functions to process data according to the specific ALMA WSU interface requirements for the correlator, and a 400G Ethernet implementation for data transmission. This firmware is currently under development and is critical for completing the high-speed data transport prototype.

F-Tile Ethernet Intel® FPGA Hard IP The F-Tile Ethernet Intel® FPGA Hard IP has been successfully tested using the example design provided by the manufacturer. The test setup involved board-to-board communication via QSFP112 connectors and copper cables, with identical firmware implementing the 200G Ethernet protocol on both sides. The functionality of the IP was verified using the Intel Ethernet Toolkit, a plugin for Intel Quartus Prime that facilitates the control and monitoring of on-board IPs through a JTAG link.

Figures 24 and 25 present the results of the initial test, which consisted of a basic status check on both boards. This test aimed to validate the IP implementation and the board-to-board communication.

The successful locking of RX CDR clocks on each side to the clock provided by the other board confirms the proper implementation of the IP and the functionality of communication through the QSFP112 connectors.

Figures 26 and 27 present the results of the second test, which focused on verifying the data rate and bit error rate on both boards. Two different modes were tested on each side. While no specific information is available regarding the expected data rates for each mode, the measured

data rates were analyzed to ensure consistency between each TX and its corresponding RX pair. Additionally, the test aimed to identify any bit errors or packet loss.

For each corresponding TX/RX pair, the observed data rates were consistent, with no packet loss or bit errors detected. These results validate the successful implementation of the 200G Ethernet communication.

Figure 24: Intel Ethernet Toolkit status check results on board A

Figure 25: Intel Ethernet Toolkit status check results on board B

Figure 26: Intel Ethernet Toolkit data rate and bit error results on board A

Figure 27: Intel Ethernet Toolkit data rate and bit error results on board B

Half-band filter DSP Builder for Intel FPGA tool was used to facilitate the translation of the algorithm using the specific blocks of the DSP Builder library. This tool allows for the efficient generation of the different IP blocks in HDL language, while optimizing the design process. The internal clock frequency is 312.5 MHz and the number of samples processed per clock cycle is 128 (40 GHz / 312.5 MHz). To validate the generated IP blocks, simulations were performed in DSP Builder (Figure 28) and Modelsim (Figure 29), ensuring that each block behave as expected. The simulation results are presented below.

Figure 28: DSP builder simulation

Figure 29: Modelsim simulation

7.2.3 FPGA and GPU server communication

For the reasons explained in Section 4, DPDK is currently chosen as the technology used for transmitting digitized data to the correlator (GPU server). Currently, communication using 200 GbE between an FPGA and the GPU server has not yet been implemented. We are still in the testing phase for implementing various QSFP modules that will ultimately enable this communication.

However, DPDK has been implemented on the current GPU server in our laboratory. Figure 30 presents the results obtained in terms of data throughput by performing an optical loopback with QSFP modules enabling 200GbE transmission, using the pktgen tool to generate traffic. These results indicate a throughput limitation at 100Gbps per TX and RX lane, which was discovered during our tests. This limitation is due to the server’s NIC, which supports a maximum bandwidth of 200 Gbps, shared between the two QSFP ports and both transmit and receive lanes. In the case of an optical loopback configuration, this results in a throughput cap of 100Gbps per lane.

To validate the use of DPDK with the prototype, it is necessary to wait until the development fo the firmware to be implemented on the iWave development kit is completed in order to transmit from the FPGA using the 200 GbE protocol.

```

/ Ports 0-1 of 2 <Main Page> Copyright(c) <2010-2023>, Intel Corporation
Port:Flags : 0:P----- Single 1:P----- Single
Link State : <UP-100000-FD> <UP-100000-FD> ---Total Rate---
Pkts/s Rx : 6 054 686 0 6 054 372 0 12 109 058 0
Tx : 6 054 272 0 6 054 656 0 12 108 928
Mbits/s Rx/Tx : 99 974/99 968 0/0 99 969/99 974 0/0 199 944/199 942
Pkts/s Rx Max : 6 055 896 0 6 055 619 0 12 111 515 0
Tx Max : 6 054 784 0 6 054 656 0 12 108 928
Broadcast : 0 0
Multicast : 0 0
Sizes 64 : 0 0
65-127 : 0 0
128-255 : 0 0
256-511 : 0 0
512-1023 : 0 0
1024-1518 : 0 0
Runts/Jumbos : 0/1 493 079 29648 0/0 0/1 493 006 78444 0/0
ARP/ICMP Pkts : 0/0 0/0
Errors Rx/Tx : 0/0 0/0
Total Rx Pkts : 20 302 046 0 20 300 605 0
Tx Pkts : 20 299 904 0 20 303 104 0
Rx/Tx MBs : 335 227/335 192 0/0 335 203/335 244 0/0
TCP Flags : .A... .A...
TCP Seq/Ack : 74616/74640 74616/74640
Pattern Type : abcd... abcd...
Tx Count/% Rate : Forever /100% Forever /100%
Pkt Size/Rx:Tx Burst: 2048 / 64: 64 2048 / 64: 64
TTL/Port Src/Dest : 64/ 1234/ 5678 64/ 1234/ 5678
Pkt Type:VLAN ID : IPv4 / TCP:0001 IPv4 / TCP:0001
802.1p CoS/DSCP/IPP : 0/ 0/ 0 0/ 0/ 0
VxLAN Flg/Grp/vid : 0000/ 0/ 0 0000/ 0/ 0
IP Destination : 192.168.1.1 192.168.0.1
Source : 192.168.0.1/24 192.168.1.1/24
MAC Destination :
Source :
NUMA/Vend:ID/PCI :-1/15b3:101b/0000:41:0-1/15b3:101b/0000:41:00.1
--- Pktgen 23.10.0 (DPDK 24.07.0) Powered by DPDK (pid:299917) -----

** Version: DPDK 24.07.0, Command Line Interface without timers
Pktgen:/> set 0,1 size 2048
Pktgen:/> start 0,1
Pktgen:/>

```

Figure 30: DPDK data rates measurement on LAB GPU server

8 Conclusion and Future Work

This demonstration successfully explored and evaluated high-speed data transport technologies, comparing DPDK and RDMA to identify the most appropriate solution for high-bandwidth applications. Both technologies showed significant advantages, each offering distinct methods of overcoming traditional bottlenecks in data transfer systems.

The DPDK implementation demonstrated outstanding performance, achieving unprecedented data rates of 1.2 Tb/s by eliminating PCIe bandwidth limitations and operating system overhead. Sending packet data directly to GPU memory and processing it further highlighted the importance of combining hardware and software innovations. Despite a considerable load on the CPU and GPU, improvements in energy efficiency, including a reduction of 145 watts through frequency tuning, preserved a balance between performance and resource utilization.

Conversely, the RDMA solution presented an efficient hardware-based approach by bypassing processor involvement when receiving data, thus reducing potential bottlenecks. The implementation of a modular architecture and an RDMA state machine for the headers ensured

flexibility and scalability, validated through extensive simulation verification. Although promising, the RDMA approach has not yet been proven on physical hardware, and the complexity of its development in firmware represents a major challenge. In view of these results, the software-based DPDK approach continues to be the preferred solution at this stage, thanks to its proven ability to achieve high data transport rates while maintaining manageable complexity. Nevertheless, work is underway to address DPDK's limitations with potential advances offered by DOCA. In particular, DOCA DPA and DOCA FlexIO are expected to further reduce the load on the CPU and GPU by optimizing memory management and data handling processes.

Even though high-speed data transport prototype is still in development, the preliminary interfacing and measurements are very promising. They pave the way for the finalization of this prototype, which will allow for the full demonstration of high-speed data transfer using the next generation digitization system that will be implemented for the ALMA WSU. These developments signify an important move toward realizing effective, scalable solutions for future high-bandwidth applications.

9 Repositories

name	repository	access
<i>radio blocks</i>		
RDMA packetiser	https://git.astron.nl/rtsd/hdl/-/tree/master/applications/rdma_demo/libraries/rdma_packetiser	open
RDMA icrc	https://git.astron.nl/rtsd/hdl/-/tree/master/applications/rdma_demo/libraries/rdma_icrc_external	open
RDMA generator	https://git.astron.nl/rtsd/hdl/-/tree/master/applications/rdma_demo/libraries/rdma_generator	open
Tensor-Core Correlator	https://git.astron.nl/RD/tensor-core-correlator	open
Tensor-Core Beam Former	https://git.astron.nl/RD/recruit/ccglib	open
<i>Prototype demonstrator applications</i>		
DPDK demo correlator	https://gitlab.eso.org/alma/gpu-correlator/dpdk-correlator	on request
RDMA demo (simulation)	https://git.astron.nl/rtsd/hdl/-/tree/master/applications/rdma_demo/libraries	open
iWave design - Agilex 7 FPGA	https://forge.oasu.u-bordeaux.fr/LAB/electronique/iwave_design	on request
Stratix 10 GX FPGA (sample capture only)	https://forge.oasu.u-bordeaux.fr/LAB/electronique/S10GX/MICRAM	on request
Half-band filter	https://forge.oasu.u-bordeaux.fr/LAB/electronique/alma_fir_filter	on request

Table 4: List of git repositories.

Table 4 lists the git repositories of the radio blocks and the prototype demonstrator applications. Most software is open access. Some newly developed software is available on request only, because the software is subject to major API changes, or does not meet certain quality standards yet. Such a repository will be opened as soon as a publication on it has been accepted.

References

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